

Reinforcing thin sheet metal using Wire Arc Additive Manufacturing For application in free-form façade construction

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ABSTRACT

Additive manufacturing with steel wire, also known as Wire Arc Additive Manufacturing (WAAM), has become increasingly important in structural engineering research in past years. WAAM enables the layer-by-layer construction of steel structures, considering the load path, so that it enables significant material savings compared to subtractive manufacturing methods.

To date, free-form sheet metal façades can only be realized using large sheet metal thicknesses, inducing high dead weights, and resulting in high material consumptions and costs. The use of WAAM to reinforce thin sheets for façade construction could offer a more ecological and economical solution. Within a research project at the TU Darmstadt, a WAAM reinforced demonstrator with a sheet thickness of 1.0 mm was developed for a rear-ventilated façade construction. Thereby, applicable welding process parameters were developed, allowing a layer-by-layer build-up of weld seams, without melting through the sheet metal. The weld metal was tested for sufficient ductility and strength in tensile tests considering the influence of active cooling on the material properties. Using a depth camera, the coordinates for the welding path were captured and automatically converted into a robot code. Alongside the material properties of the weld metal, the weld-induced deformation of the sheet metal plays a decisive role. Within a parameter study, the uniaxial weld-induced deformation of sheet metal strips measuring 200 x 1000 cm was quantified both experimentally and numerically in relation to the weld layer height. The experimental study was carried out on flat and elastically pre-curved sheets using a frame with a radius of 5 m. Working with a depth camera, the coordinates for the welding path were captured and automatically converted into the robot code. A statistical model was used to investigate whether the curvature of the sheet metal strips can be represented by a parabolic or circular function.

Keywords: Wire Arc Additive Manufacturing, sheet metal, welding-induced deformation, façade construction

1 INTRODUCTION

Additive Manufacturing (AM) characterizes the layer-by-layer fabrication of a structure. Thereby, different materials, usually fluid, powder, past-like or molten, can be used (1). By the improvement of automation over the past years, additive manufacturing became more relevant, and several research and industrial fields focused on this technology (1). To name just a few materials, steel, sand, polymers, and concrete are already established in aerospace- and civil engineering but also in medicine and architecture (2; 3; 4). Two main reasons for AM are the significant material savings compared to subtractive manufacturing methods, and the ability to create more complex and detailed three dimensional structures (5). The side effects of these opportunities are inter alia more efficient material usage and less importance of human resource leading to significant cost savings (1; 5).

1.1 Wire Arc Additive Manufacturing

Wire Arc Additive Manufacturing (WAAM) or Direct Energy Deposition-Arc AM (DED-AM) describe a 3D-printing method, using a welding power source and a robot or gantry system (6; 7). In research and industry gas shield metal arc welding (GMAW) or laser assisted metal deposition are commonly used deposition methods (3; 7). This paper focuses on GMAW, using the CMT Cycle Step welding process from Fronius (8). Working with GMAW, allows high deposition rates and at the same time appropriate accuracy for structural engineering applications. Besides the manufacturing advantages of GMAW material properties of mild- and stainless-steel specimen have been widely studied inter alia in (9; 10) and lately summarized by Gardner (11). However, WAAM material properties are not predictable due to different welding devices, process parameters and shielding gases. Therefore, new material properties must be determined for any new process.

1.2 Sheet metal in façade construction

Two famous examples of free form sheet metal façade constructions are the Walt Disney Opera House in San Francisco and the Cloud Gate in Chicago, shown in Figure 1. To realize and obtain the shape of Cloud Gate, steel sheet thicknesses of 6 mm had to be used (12).

Fig. 1. Cloud Gate, Chicago

Sheet thickness and weight have already been reduced using new composite façade systems (13; 14) or thinner steel sheets of approx. 2.0 mm (15). Considering the ecologic aspect of hard to recycle polymers and high dead weights of a 2.0 mm mild steel sheet metal façade a more ecologic and economic solution for free form metal façade constructions is needed. Reinforcing thin steel sheet metal using WAAM seems to be an opportunity to overcome those issues. Borg (4) already showed architectural possibilities and reinforced examples and prototypes of reinforced thin steel sheets. As he mentions in his dissertation, welding induced distortion is one of the most relevant problems to overcome.

1.3 Welding distortions

In figure 2 typical shrinkage behaviours of welded steel sheets are shown, leading to different forms of distortion or buckling. For the reinforcement of thin steel sheet metal using WAAM, within this paper bending distortion in longitudinal direction and buckling become significant. Although angular distortion occurs, it gets reduced by the high distortions in longitudinal direction, as shown later in this paper. For the use of WAAM, buckling must be prevented to be able to use robot coordinates for a layer-by-layer built-up of the reinforcing welding ribs. Therefore, appropriate clamping methods of the sheet metal are crucial.

Fig. 2. typical shrinking and distortion behaviours (16)

To predict deformations and estimate residual stresses, FEM modelling can be used. Looking on different options to model heat sources, using a Goldak power density distribution has emerged as the strategy with the most accurate approximation of a welding heat source, due to its double ellipsoidal shape (17). The accuracy of a modelled Goldak heat source depends on the geometric approximation of the welding seam and the process parameters given by a weld-scanning system. Figure 3 shows a Goldak heat source suitable for the welding parameters used in this paper. For accurate results in small models, so-called birth and death methods are often used. Hereby, the modelled weld seam element appears within the welding simulation just when the heat source reaches its place. For large scale models, as in façade construction or civil engineering, this method leads to high computing time.

Fig. 3. Goldak Power density distribution

2 DEFORMATION PREDICTION

As mentioned in 1.2, the welding induced deformation is the biggest challenge when welding on thin sheet metal. Within a research project at TU Darmstadt, it was the goal to fabricate a WAAM reinforced rear-ventilated free-form façade panel using a DC01 cold-rolled sheet metal with the dimension 2000 x 1000 x 1 mm. There are two ways to create a free form façade panel. Firstly, it is possible to elastically or plastically deform the sheet metal and weld the stiffening ribs on the backside

afterwards. Secondly, the welding induced deformation can be used to deform a flat sheet into a free form shape. Therefore, the deformation behaviour must be investigated and a model how to quantify the deformation must be found. First tests on plastically deformed sheets showed, that on one hand the formwork to preform and the clamping for the welding part led to high material consumption and waste for each shape. On the other hand, it was not possible to just maintain the preformed shape due to additional welding induced deformation due to the stiffening ribs. The coordinates for the welding and the differences of the shape before and after welding were given by a research project partner using a depth camera. Figure 4 shows a preformed sheet metal with stiffening welding ribs. The welding process parameters have been investigated in former parameter studies and material properties have been determined (18). A picture of the welding seam used in this paper is shown in Figure 5. Further testing on various sheet thicknesses have shown that the parameters can be used to weld on 0.75 mm sheet thicknesses without burning through the bottom surface.

Fig. 4. a) preforming process; b) welded ribs

Fig 5. Example of a welding seam with 20 layers for tensile coupons

Subsequently, upcoming studies focused on the quantification and numerical verification to predict and use welding induced deformation. These studies will be discussed more detailed within this publication.

A six-axis COMAU Smart NM 16-3.1 robotic system and a Fronius CMT 4000 Advanced heat source with a 0.8 mm ER70S-6 wire in combination with a M21 shielding gas mixture was used. The main welding parameters used can be found in Table 1. DC01 sheet metal specimen with a geometry of 1000 x 200 x 1 mm have been reinforced. The sheets were clamped on the longitudinal edges and a welding seam length of 950 mm has been applied, see Figure 6. The number of layers varied from 1 to 10. The height and width of one welding seam is approximately 1.0 mm. Furthermore, the influence of welding on flat and on elastically preformed specimen on a frame has been investigated. The frame had a circular shape with a radius of 5 m.

Table 1. welding parameters

Welding Process	Wire Feed Speed (WFS) nominal in m/min	Travel Speed (TS) in mm/min	CTWD in mm	Cycles	Interval Break in ms
CMT Cycle-Step	3.6	400	10	2	4

Fig. 6. Schematic sketch of the clamped sheet

The numerical simulations have been performed only on flat specimen using Ansys Workbench. A multilinear plasticity hardening model was generated using the results of (18). The mesh was split into three different sizes going from a close mesh in the welding seam area to a wider mesh size around the long edges of the sheet to reduce calculation time. The Goldak heat source geometry was adjusted to the approximated weld seam of 1.0 x 1.0 mm. The model was split with a symmetry axis to reduce calculating time. A thermal transient analysis was conducted. The results of the thermal analysis were then transferred into a static mechanic analysis to evaluate the deformation.

2.1 Deformation of flat and elastically pre-bent sheets

There were three specimens of each number of layers welded from 1 to 10. The sheets have been clamped on the longitudinal edges to the frame or rather flat above the welding table using square hollow profiles. Figure 7 shows the frame and a released sheet specimen turned upside down showing its heat affected zone. The number of clamps had to be sufficient, so that the longitudinal edges do not lift off the frame due to welding distortions.

Fig. 7. Welded sheet laying upside down on the frame

Figure 9 shows the measured maximum vertical deformation in the middle of the chord to the sheet. Reference measurements have shown the same results on the sheet edges and next to the welding seam. The negative measurements of the specimen with one, two, and three layers welding on elastically pre-bent sheets illustrate the inverse deformation with reference to the expected form due to longitudinal shrinking of the welding seams. The inverse deformation could be caused by a stability problem within the first layers. It is to mention that the measurements of 4 layers welded on the frame could be either listed with a negative or positive value, due to an unsteady deformation behaviour, see Figure 8. Though, this phenomenon does not occur while welding on flat sheets. The measurement results show a maximum at 3 layers (flat) and 5 layers (pre-bent) steadily decreasing until 10 layers for both, pre-bent, and flat sheets.

Fig. 8. a) “positive” deformation; b) “negative” deformation

Fig. 9. Deformation of flat sheets (grey), elastically pre-bent sheets (black), FEA (red)

2.2 Numerical simulation

To validate the experimental parameter study, finite-element analysis (FEA) has been conducted using Ansys 2023 R1. As already mentioned, the multilinear plasticity hardening material model was generated with the results of former material testing (18). Using a HKS P1000 weld scanner, the average values of 20.75 V and 32.69 A have been determined and used to calibrate the Goldak heat source. The melting temperature of the wire has been defined at 1500°C, considering the carbon composition of the ER70S-6 wire. The FEA has been performed also for 1 to 10 welding layers. Figure 9 shows the FEA results in red, together with the experimental results. Within the first three layers, there are differences of 23.5 to 12.5 mm between the FEA and the experimental results. From layer 5 on, the FEA results almost correspond to the experimental results. The general course of the FEA results also fits both experimental test series.

2.3 Geometry Definition

Within this test series, the focus was put on the maximum deformation in the middle of the chord. Of course, the overall shape of the specimen is interesting, and whether it follows a function. Using a Matlab Script, the values at $X = 0$, and the maximum deformation in the middle of the chord h , a comparison was carried out whether the deformation of the specimen does fit a circular or a parabola shape, see coordinate system in Figure 10. Therefore, two functions (circular and parabola shape) were determined using the average value of the maximum deformation of all specimens of each layer number. Afterwards, the functions were compared with the deformations measured at $x = \pm 0.25 \cdot L$.

Table 2 shows the measurements of one of the specimens with 5 welded layers (specimen 5.2) compared to the circular and parabola functions. It shows that both functions do not have noticeable deviations to each other. However, to be able to make a prediction, the Bayesian Information Criterion (BIC) (19; 20) has been used to measure the quality of the model (circular vs. parabola function). The lower the BIC is, the more a model fits to the experimental results. For specimen 5.2 the application of the BIC has brought the following results, $BIC_{circle} = 10.1 < BIC_{parabola} = 14.3$. This leads to the assumption that the welded specimens do rather describe a circular than a parabola shape. Though, to make more accurate assumptions, welding on longer specimens could be appropriate to reach higher deviations between the circular and parabola model. Furthermore, the more the shape of the specimen fit the circular function, the less the deviations between both functions are, because the parabola function then approximates the circular function.

Fig. 10. Coordinate system for geometry definition

Table 2. Extract of Lab and Matlab Data of specimen 5.2

X	specimen 5.2	Parabola	Circle
-495.85	0	0	0
-247,93	49.0	46.8	46.9
0	64.0	62.3	62.3
247,93	50.0	46.8	46.9
495.85	0	0	0

3 SUMMARY AND ACKNOWLEDGMENT

To predict welding induced distortions in reinforced thin sheet metal using Wire Arc Additive Manufacturing, this paper focused on the uniaxial distortion of sheet metal specimens with 1.0 mm thickness. The experimental studies were performed on flat sheets and elastically pre-bent sheets on a frame with a 5.0 m radius. Additionally, a numerical approach was given, analysing the flat welded sheets using Ansys Workbench. The maximum deformation in the middle of the chord of the sheets was measured. The experimental studies both showed similar deformation behaviour. Furthermore, the results given by the calculations in Ansys showed almost equal distortions, see Figure 9. The decreasing deformation after a certain layer number, could be explained by the fact that residual stresses in the sheet can be released due to reheating after each welded layer.

In 2.3 an attempt was made to define the shape of the welded specimen. The results show that the shape does rather fit a circular than a parabola shape. Though, the differences between both models (circular and parabola) are marginally. Welding on longer specimen could lead to higher deviations between the models.

Furthermore, the influence of other sheet thicknesses and geometries, and the use of parallel welding ribs should be further investigated to broaden the results of this paper to a more complex model for the deformation prediction of thin sheet metal reinforced using WAAM.

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